

Studies on Phenothiazines. I. Synthesis of Some New Biologically Active 10(*p*-Azetidionyl- and Thiazolidinoyl-benzenesulphonyl) Phenothiazines

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Ten(*p*-substituted arylidenesulphanilyl) phenothiazines(III) have been prepared via condensation of 10-sulfanilylphenothiazine(II) with substituted aromatic aldehydes. Interaction of III with chloroacetyl chloride and mercaptoacetic acid gave 10(*p*-azetidionylbenzenesulphonyl) phenothiazines(IV) and 10(*p*-thiazolidinoylbenzenesulphonyl) phenothiazines(V), respectively. The prepared compounds(III, IV and V) were screened against some strains of bacteria and fungi. Results showed that compounds III_b, III_d, III_n, III_r, IV_b, V_g and V_h were the most active bacterial inhibitors.

PHENOTHIAZINES are very useful compounds in many different aspects. They are widely used as antioxidants for some lubricating oils¹. In the field of medicine, they are ideal for development of various drugs, some phenothiazine derivatives are now being used as anthelmintics², antihistaminics³ and suppressors⁴. A part from the foregoing applications, some secondary-aminoalkyl-phenothiazine were reported to possess antimicrobial activities⁵.

Results and Discussion

Since the antibacterial effect of sulphanilamide has been attributed to the presence of a sulphonamide groups ($-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$) and an $-\text{NH}_2$ group in para position, it is of interest to study the effect of fixation of these groups to the phenothiazine moiety. This interest has also prompted us to extend this study to include the effect of the introduction of the well known antibacterial nuclei (azetidione and thiazolidinone) instead of $-\text{NH}_2$ group into the phenothiazine nucleus. With these objectives in mind, several 10-substituted arylidinesulphanilyl-phenothiazine have been prepared as an extension to our previous work in this subject⁶.

p-Acetylaminobenzenesulphonyl chloride was condensed with phenothiazine according to the method described by Bernstein and Rothstein⁷. The resulting 10(*p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphanilyl)phenothiazine(I) was hydrolysed readily to 10(*p*-aminobenzenesulphanilyl) phenothiazine(II) with sodium hydroxide solution.

Alcoholic solution of 10(*p*-aminobenzenesulphanilyl) phenothiazine(II) was reacted easily with substituted aromatic aldehydes in presence of piperidine as a catalyst, giving 10(*p*-substituted arylidenesulphanilyl) phenothiazines(III).

Ar = C_6H_5 ; *o*-OH. C_6H_4 ; *p*-OCH₃. C_6H_4 ; *p*-NO₂. C_6H_4 ; *p*-Cl. C_6H_4 ; *m*-NO₂. C_6H_4 ; 2-OH-5-NO₂. C_6H_3 ; Furfuryl; Pipronyl and Ferrocenyl.

The structure of these compounds(III) has been established from their correct analytical data (cf. Table 1) and spectroscopic analysis. The i.r. spectra of these compounds showed absorption bands at 1630 cm^{-1} (for $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ group) and at 1175 cm^{-1} (for $-\text{SO}_2\text{N}$ group)⁸.

Cycloaddition of chloroacetyl chloride on III, in dry dioxane solvent and triethylamine as a catalyst, gave 10(*p*-azetidionylbenzenesulphonyl) phenothiazines(IV) in good yields. The reaction can be

represented as follows :

Elemental analysis (cf. Table 2) as well as spectroscopic analysis of IV are in accordance with the suggested structures. For example, i.r. spectra reveals an absorption bands at 1180 cm^{-1} for $-\text{SO}_2\text{N}$ group, and at 1740 cm^{-1} for $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group (monocyclic β -Lactam)⁸. On the other hand, cyclocondensation of mercaptoacetic acid with III, in dry benzene, produced 10(*p*-thiazolidinoylbenzenesulphonyl) phenothiazine(V).

The structure of compounds V was established from the microanalytical data and i.r. spectra. A characteristic absorption bands at 1175 cm^{-1} (for $-\text{SO}_2\text{N}$ group) and at 1750 cm^{-1} (for $-\text{C}=\text{O}$ group) were observed⁸.

Antimicrobial Activities :

The antimicrobial activities of the prepared compounds against a variety of microbes were determined. These microorganisms include Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria as well as some fungi.

Three different concentrations of each compound were prepared in ethylene glycol (0.1 mg./ml., 1 mg./ml. and 2 mg./ml.) and tested by the paper disc technique.

Results showed that all the compounds tested were inactive against fungi but active against bacteria particularly *Bacillus subtilis* from the gram-positive bacteria and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from the gram-negative bacteria. In this respect the derivatives III_b, III_d, III_h, III_i, IV_b, V_a, and V_h were the most active and were similar in their potency to the parent compound II.

Experimental

All melting points were uncorrected and were obtained, on a Kopfler electrically heated melting point. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam I.R. Spectrophotometer, SP 200 G.

10(Arylidene, Ferrocenylidene and Furfurylidene) Sulphanilyl phenothiazines(III) :

An alcoholic solution of 0.01 mole of II, slight excess of the aromatic aldehyde and drops of piperidine was refluxed for three hours. The reaction mixture was then concentrated, cooled, the produced solid was separated by filtration and recrystallized from the proper solvent see (Table 1).

10(*p*-Azetidinoylbenzenesulphonyl)phenothiazines(IV) :

Chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mole) was added to a mixture of 0.01 mole of the Schiff's base(III) and 0.005 mole triethylamine in 15 ml of dry benzene. The reaction mixture was refluxed while stirring for two hours. At the end of the reflux period, the solution was concentrated and worked up as before to give the pure products, as indicated in Table 2.

TABLE 1—10-SUBSTITUTED ARYLIDENESULFANILYLPHENOTHIAZINES (III)

Compound (Ar)	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analytical data*			
				Calculated% N	S	Observed% N	S
a- C ₆ H ₅ -	187-8	75	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	6.33	7.24	6.55	7.30
b- o-C ₆ H ₄ OH-	218-220	95	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	6.11	6.99	5.98	7.04
c- 2,5-C ₆ H ₃ (OH) ₂ -	208-5	71.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₃	8.35	6.36	8.78	6.45
d- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl-	203-4	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂ Cl	5.87	6.72	6.09	7.00
e- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	216.7	73	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	8.62	6.57	8.58	6.77
f- <i>m</i> -8H ₄ NO ₂ -	192.4	69	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	8.62	6.57	8.94	6.60
g- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -	201.2	70	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	5.97	13.56	6.09	13.90
h- C ₆ H ₅ FeC ₆ H ₄ -	203.4	96	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂ Fe	5.09	5.82	5.33	6.01
i- C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ CO ₂ -	120.2	40	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₄	5.76	6.58	5.90	6.42
j- C ₄ H ₉ O-	159-61	60	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ S ₂ O ₂	6.48	7.41	6.57	7.52

* Satisfactory analysis for C and H were also obtained.

The used bacteria includes : *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The fungi were, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Penicillium notatum*, *Trichoderma viridi* and *Fusarium solani*.

10(*p*-Thiazolidinoylbenzenesulphonyl)phenothiazines(V) :

Mercaptoacetic acid (0.06 mole) was added to a well stirred solution of 0.05 mole of Schiff's base III in 50 ml dry benzene. Stirring was continued for

TABLE 2—10(*p*-AZEPIDINOYL BENZENESULPHONYL) PHENOTHIAZINES (IV)

Compound (Ar)	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analytical data*			
				Calculated %		Observed %	
				N	S	N	S
a- C ₆ H ₅ -	196-97	34	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	5.44	12.34	5.50	12.5
b- C ₆ H ₅ OH-	195-96	30	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	5.24	11.97	5.34	12.00
c- 2,5-C ₆ H ₃ (OHNO ₂)-	179-80	52	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.25	11.04	7.32	11.40
d- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl-	108-110	36	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl ₂	5.06	11.57	5.16	11.64
e- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	90-92	48	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.45	11.36	7.50	11.66
f- <i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	166-67	36	C ₂₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	7.45	11.36	7.54	11.44
g- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -	189-90	43	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	5.11	11.67	5.09	11.99
h- C ₆ H ₅ FeC ₆ H ₄ -	130-32	40	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ S ₂ O ₄ ClFe	4.47	10.22	4.59	10.92
i- C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ (O ₂)-	113-14	38	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	4.98	11.38	5.03	11.40
j- C ₆ H ₅ O-	122-24	42	C ₂₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	5.51	12.59	5.58	12.50

* Satisfactory analysis for C and H were also obtained.

TABLE 3—10(*p*-THIAZOLIDINOYL BENZENESULPHONYL) PHENOTHIAZINES (V)

Compound (Ar)	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analytical data*			
				Calculated %		Observed %	
				N	S	N	S
a- C ₆ H ₅ -	182-88	73	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	5.43	18.60	5.55	18.77
b- C ₆ H ₅ OH-	100-2	75	C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	5.26	18.05	5.32	17.99
c- 2,5-C ₆ H ₃ (OHNO ₂)-	102-3	75	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	4.85	16.64	5.04	16.50
d- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl-	109-111	65	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Cl	5.09	17.44	5.11	17.77
e- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	120-121	60	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	4.99	17.11	5.04	17.03
f- <i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ -	135-36	75	C ₂₇ H ₁₈ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	4.99	17.11	5.10	17.00
g- <i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ -	92-94	68	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	5.13	17.58	5.46	17.68
h- C ₆ H ₅ FeC ₆ H ₄ -	172-74	42	C ₃₁ H ₂₄ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄ Fe	4.49	15.39	4.90	15.40
i- C ₆ H ₅ O-	114-15	58	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	5.53	18.97	5.66	19.02
j- C ₆ H ₅ OH(O ₂)-	97-98	71	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₃ S ₂ O ₄	5.00	17.14	5.09	17.24

* Satisfactory analysis for C and H were also obtained.

three hours. On cooling, a precipitate was formed, filtered and crystallized from the proper solvents. Results are tabulated in Table 3.

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